

The Dynamics of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPHS) Levels in the Body of Water in Ethiope River, Delta State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This research investigated the levels of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPHs) levels in the polluted surface water body of River Ethiope, Delta State, Nigeria. Three remediation methods (Bioremediation, Silica encapsulation and Surfactant methods) were employed as to ascertain the best remediation efficacy. The physicochemical parameters of the polluted river water samples were determined prior to and after analysis and results showed that most of the parameters were within the maximum permissible limit for drinking water in Nigeria. Levels of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPHs) in the surface river water samples were extracted separately using standard analytical methods and examined with the Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS) before and after analysis. Results revealed that there was a diminishing TPHs trend in all samples on employing the three remediation techniques. Bioremediation method gave the optimum remediation efficiency on administering the second dose of treatment, the highest percentage remediation of 94.48 while optimum remediation was obtained on administering the first dose for the silica encapsulation and surfactant methods respectively (94.11 and 92.56). The kinetics of remediation revealed that all plots of graph were linear with regression coefficient, R^2 for the pseudo first order fittings, highly close to 1 ($R^2 = 0.9968$) in all the samples. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that there was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) at 95% confidence limit in the various remediation techniques but in terms of the treatment dosage, there was a significant difference in the bioremediation method ($P < 0.05$) at 95 confidence level. Based on the expected findings, it was recommended that in the event of oil spill, involving contamination of all compartments of the marine habitat such as the water surface, water column, sediments, only one single spill response strategy is unlikely to provide optimal protection. Therefore, effort should be made by management bodies to adopt two or multiple techniques.

Keywords: Bioremediation, encapsulation, pseudo-first order, regression coefficient,

1.0 Introduction

Deliberate or accidental discharge of petroleum hydrocarbons and its derivatives into the marine habitat has become a major concern in these recent times especially since crude oil was discovered in 1956. These petroleum products contain organic pollutants such as aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons of C₅-C₃₅ chains collectively known as total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) that requires a close monitoring in an environment (Adeniji *et al.*, 2018). Monitoring the physicochemical parameters and TPHs of water quality parameters plays a vital role in assessing the water environment, ecosystem, hydrochemistry and ecology and foster total restoration of the aquatic environment [Sarkar *et al.*, 2016; Whitehead *et al.*, 2018; Islam *et al.*, 2019]. TPHs may be defined as the measurable amount of aliphatic, alicyclic and aromatic hydrocarbon present in a petroleum-based organic content (Olayinka *et al.*, 2021). The pathway of TPHs often spilled in marine environment is enormous as it is highly undegradable by microorganisms and tend to remain persistent in the water media (Sari *et al.*, 2018). Ozdemir, (2018) reported that water bodies associated with hydrocarbons spill typically contain high concentrations of dissolved organic and inorganic minerals which may negatively impact the physicochemical processes of the aquatic environment as it has the tendency to bio-accumulate in tissues of aquatic organisms and humans as well (Adeniji *et al.*, 2019) TPHs compounds such as poly aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are genotoxic, mutatoxic, carcinogenic and/or teratogenic and may alter the endocrine system at levels higher than maximum allowable limit in a short period of time [Brazkova & Krastanov, 2013; Adeniji *et al.*, 2018]. There have been a considerable number of studies on TPHs pollution of surface water and groundwater in Nigeria [Adewuyi & Olowu, 2012; Daniel & Nna, 2016; Aniefiok *et al.*, 2018; Olayinka *et al.*, 2021].

Small oil spills often resulting, natural disasters and human activities had been recorded over the years in the Niger Delta zone of Nigeria. Spill experts estimate that 30-50% of oil spills are either directly or indirectly caused by human from accidental leakages error, with 20-40% of all spills caused by equipment failure or malfunction (Michel and Fingas, 2016). Water resources are under severe threat from pollution generated by human interventions and inappropriate discharge of oil spill, poor agricultural drainage, and other anthropogenic activities into water bodies (Jin *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b). The oil producing communities within the coastal region where oil and gas exploration is prominent had been at the receiving end of such occurrences and such issues, of course had brought a lot of controversies within the three levels of government and the recipient communities (Anderson and LaBelle, 2000).

Recently, River Ethiope witnessed oil spillage that ran across most villages like Adagbrasa in Abraka, Eku, Okuesajere and most rivers in Ovuore and Amukpe communities within Delta State. This was as a result of pipeline accidental leakage of NNPC/PPMC. Till date, the communities affected have suffered domestic source of water supply, aquatic life deterioration, food scarcity and set back low production of agricultural products such as fish, palm oil cassava and yam due to land devastation, to mention just a few. Over 700 local fish ponds and above 5000 oil palm plantations have been affected by the oil spill in these region and has consequently resulted to the displacement and rehabilitation of the inhabitants to other communities.

Current remediation techniques are physical, chemical, thermal and biological methods (Larson, 2010; Hamby, 2012). Scientific researches based of issues relating to oil spill clean-up has gained global

attention in recent times probably due to its adverse effect on the ecosystem at large. The severity of the impact of an oil spill depends on the quantity of the oil and its chemical

Assessing the magnitude of water quality decline, clustered monitoring of the physicochemical parameters of water identified through their potential pollution sources is of paramount importance. Arafat *et al.*, (2021) monitored the seasonal variation of the physicochemical properties in the urban river of Bangladesh and revealed that BOD₅, COD EC and DO pollution loading were mainly as a result of industrial discharge into the water body.

Petroleum products from oil pipelines installed in the axis of Ndemili, Akoku –Ebedei through to Umukwata within Ukwuani LGA of Delta State could impact the water quality of Ethiope River due to their dispersing nature, persistency and carcinogenicity and thereby impacting negatively on public health of the local communities. Previous study have reported water quality degradation of Ethiope River emanating from crude oil spillage across local stream and communities of Abraka, Adabrasa, Eku, Ovuorhe through to Amukpe in recent times. Seasonal trends of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon in the sediment of River Ethiope, in Delta State has also been reported by Edjere *et al.*, (2020) and predicted that levels of PAHs within the sediments may cause adverse effects on the aquatic organisms in the aquatic environment.

Fig 1: Image of Oil Spill in River Ethiope

Materials and Methods

Map of Study Area

Fig 2: Map of Study Area

Description of Study Area

River Ethiope source is located in a village known as Umuaja in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. It flows across four Local Government Areas namely: Ukwuani, Ethiope East, Okpe and Sapele. The River flows through the densely populated evergreen forests for about 40 km through neighboring villages of Umutu, Obiaruku, Abraka, Eku, Aghalokpe and Sapele in Delta State, Nigeria. The River which is tidal at its lower base is one of the two tributaries of the Benin River.

Sample Collection and Sampling Technique

Ten (10) surface water samples was collected from the various Ethiope River stretching from Umutu through Obiaruku Abraka, Eku, Aghalokpe and Sapele, Delta state, Nigeria. Samples were taken in triplicates from the five sampling points at different locations. Composite sampling were carried out by collecting water samples from the surface of the river and 150 m depth at two- hourly intervals for over 20 hours period and the flow rate measured each time of collection. Thereafter, a single composite sampling was made by mixing together the 10 separate two- hourly samples, using volumes proportional to the flow rate at the time of sampling. The samples were put in 250 ml capacity ground-glass-stoppered that has been thoroughly washed and oven dried at 200°C.

Preparation of samples

The surface water samples from the various sampling sites were loaded with 25g of the organic supplement and stirred thoroughly. The oil spill in the polluted water samples serve as a source of nutrients for the microorganisms to enable proper remediation.

Sample Extraction

The water samples was extracted according to the methods of USEPA 510C, (1996). 40 ml of hexane was added to a separating funnel containing 250 ml of unfiltered water sample and this was shaken vigorously

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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for about 5 mins. The sample was allowed to stand for 20 minutes until two distinct layers was formed. The lower layer (the extract) was filtered into a beaker through a filter paper containing glass wool and anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na_2SO_4). The process was repeated twice using 20 ml of hexane. The extracts was combined and concentrated by evaporation at room temperature overnight in a fume cupboard by covering with a perforated aluminium foil.

Determinations of physicochemical properties of Surface water Samples

pH

The pH of the water samples was determined using a pH meter of model, pHS-25 prior to and after treatment. Here, 100ml of the sample was measured into a beaker and the pH meter electrode will then be inserted into the sample and the reading was displayed on the screen of the electrode and recorded.

Turbidity

The turbidity of the water samples were determined using Waz-B model turbidimeter after initial calibration of the instrument using the manufacturer's certified reference materials (<0.1, 10, 100, 500 and 1000 Nephelological Turbidity Unit (NTU), following the procedures lay down in the manufacturers' manual guide.

Dissolved Oxygen (D.O)

Dissolved oxygen of the water sample was determined using a Dissolved Oxygen Analyzer, model JPB – 607 Portable meter after initial calibration following the procedures provided in the manufacturers' manual. This was carried out by employing the method of Ademoroti, (1996b).

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)

The water samples was thoroughly aerated and dissolved oxygen determination was carried out as described above on a portion of the water samples, following the method of Ademoroti, (1996b).

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

Chemical oxygen demand was determined, using the dichromate reflux method as described by Ademoroti (1996b).

Equations for the reaction:

Total dissolved solids

The total dissolved solid of the water sample was determined using total dissolved solids (TDS) meter.

Total suspended solids

The total suspended solids were determined using a spectrophotometer as described in the prescription manual.

Total solids = Total dissolved solids + total suspended solids.

Electrical Conductivity

The Electrical Conductivity of the water sample was measured using a conductivity meter.

Inorganic Phosphate

Inorganic Phosphates in the water sample consisting of orthophosphate and polyphosphate was determined using the procedures as described by (Ademoroti, (1996b)). **3. Ammonia**

Ammonia in the water samples was determined following the procedures as described by (Ademoroti (1996)).

Nitrate

Nitrate in the water samples was determined following procedures described by (Ademoroti, (1996b)).

Total Alkalinity

Alkalinity in the water sample was measured following method described by Ademoroti, (1996).

Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPHs) determination

Total petroleum hydrocarbon in the water samples was analyzed using high efficiency Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS) Agilent 5977C single quadrupole GC/MSD Model. According to the manual description, the system is equipped with a 32-position sampler tray, 10/20 ml agitator. The system is equipped with HydroInert (hydrogen carrier gas)-100 fg OFN, 1 μ L injected: 1DL 50 fg. The hydroInert source prevents disruptions due to helium shortages without compromising spectral fidelity and also avoids undesirable-in-source chemistry associated with H₂ carrier gas. The GC is built with split/splitless inlet working mode to a 0m x 0.250 mm DB-1 MS column with a 0.25 μ m film thickness with an oven temperature of 40°C (held in 10 min), heating up to 240°C (held up to 20 min) with a flow rate of 1 mL/min. MS detection was conducted in the mode of scanning ions in the range of m/z 0.6-1091.

Working standards solutions for the aliphatic hydrocarbons and its halogen derivatives was prepared from the stock solutions and kept in amber bottles below 4°C. The calibration standards range of 0.05-20 μ g L^{-1} was prepared with n-hexane and used for the calibration of the instrument. The Agilent Chemstation chromatography software (OpenLab CDS) was used to generate average response factor for each analyte from the calibration curves plotted.

Remediation Analysis (Chemical Method)

For the purpose of comparison, three remediation methods were used. They are the bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant method.

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11359429>

Optimization treatment

Preparation of sodium dodecyl sulphate treatment solution for surfactant method

Several concentrations of 10,000-90,000 mg/l of sodium dodecyl sulphate solutions were prepared by dissolving 1-9g of sodium dodecyl sulphate in 9 different volumetric flasks (100cm³). These were shaken thoroughly and made up to mark using distilled water. The solutions were left overnight for proper dissolution.

Optimization of concentration and pH of treatment solutions were determined to ascertain the optimum condition for TPH removal in the methods used in this study.

Kinetics study on the Chemical method

Solutions of 4.6ml of sodium dodecyl sulphate of concentration of 50,000mg/l as obtained from the optimization study above were prepared and added to 14ml distilled water containing 1.4ml of crude oil in 30ml vials. The pH of the solutions in the vials were adjusted to pH= 3 and pH=8, the vials were properly sealed with Teflon films and shaken for 1 hour using a mechanical shaker at 200 revolutions per minute (r.p.m.). The crude oil in the water layers were separated from the crude oil in the dodecyl matrix using separatory funnels. Crude oil in the water layers were extracted GC-MS according to the manual description.

Remediation Analysis (Bioremediation Method)

Organic supplement

The moss was obtained from long abandoned, uncompleted buildings within Obiaruku community while the abathior wastes were obtained from an abathior located in Agbor. The brewery wastes will be obtained from Guinness brewery factory in Warri while the piggery wastes and fish pond wastes were obtained from an animal farm within Obiaruku community. The wastes were air-dried, ground and 25g of each were thoroughly mixed in a ratio of 1:1:1:1:1.

Microbiological analysis

Isolation and enumeration of heterotrophic and hydrocarbon utilizing Bacteria

Both heterotrophic and hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria were isolated and enumerated through a bacteria enrichment process using modified mineral salt medium as stated by Tankeshar, (2013). The composition of the mineral salt medium were as follows; NaCl-10.0g; MgSO₄·7H₂O-0.42g, KCl-0.2g, KH₂PO₄-0.83g, NaHPO₄-1.25g; NaNO₃-0.42g; deionized water 1 litre, at pH 7.2.

For the enumeration of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria, the medium was solidified by the addition of 1.5% agar. The vapour phase method was adopted for the isolation of hydrocarbon utilizers. For total heterotrophic bacteria counts, nutrient agar was used. 10 mls of test sample was withdrawn from various microcosms on each analysis day (0, 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, and 42). This was diluted using the 10 fold serial dilution technique. 0.1 ml of appropriate dilution was then plated out onto the surface of freshly prepared nutrient agar plate using the spread plate technique as described by APHA, (1995).

Characterization of isolates

Characterization of isolates were carried out using Gram staining reaction as prescribed by Patol, (2014). Citrate utilization test; Motility test; Spore staining; Oxidase test. These tests were performed as described by Tankeshar, (2013).

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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Kinetics of bioremediation

Changes in total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) with time were monitored on weekly basis for the polluted microcosms for 6 weeks. TPH analyses were carried out using GC-MS spectrophotometer

Statistical Analysis

Statistical treatment was achieved by preparing samples in triplicates. Statistical tool used was Standard Deviation (SD), Coefficient of Variation (CV) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was employed to checkmate intermediate or random error Blanks runs was also conducted to reduce determinate errors so as to make the results to be of high precision.

Results

Table 1 showed the comparison of the physicochemical parameters of the water samples with FMEnv and WHO standards prior to and after analysis.

Table 1: Comparison of Physicochemical parameters Prior to and after Analysis of water samples with FMEnv and WHO standards.

	Bioremediation		Silica encapsulation		Surfactant		FMEnv	WHO
	Prior	After	Prior	After	Prior	After		
pH	6.50	8.20	6.70	9.10	6.90	10.30	8.50–9.50	6.5-8.5
Turbidity	1,250.10±16.50	118.20±24.23	584.33±0.06	7.67± 0.12	559.20±0.15	10.30±0.10		5
D.O (mg/L)	3.20±0.01	4.50±0.15	4.00±0.10	5.80±0.12	4.30±0.06	4.80±0.25	15.00	10.00
Temp 0C	28.70±0.20	28.50±0.25	28.65±0.12	28.25±0.15	28.50±0.05	28.30±0.17		28-30
BOD ₅ (mg /L)	11.30±1.20	4.70±1.53	9.20±2.00	5.66±1.80	9.50±0.80	8.45±2,20	5-7.5	
COD (mg/L)	388.00±0.20	35.25±0.20	315.75±0.50	67.55±0.15	322.42±0.30	80.60±0.16	40.00	
TDS (mg/L)	120.15±1.20	58.65±1.90	118.50±1.70	52.42±2.53	112.70±1.50	98.20±1.25		400
EC (µS/cm)	106.00±2.5	1,118.00±1.5	110.00±2.2	1,108.00±1.0	108.00±1.6	950.00±1.3	1,200	400-1000
PO ₃ ⁴⁻ (mg/L)	0.36±0.06	0.04± 0.8	0.40±0.25	0.06±0.03	0.45±2.1	0.07±0.08	0.5	-
NH ₃ (mg/L)	0.22±0.75	3.10±0.58	0.33±0.63	0.48±0.70	0.20±1.50	0.42±0.17	0.5	-
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	36.00±2.0	21.00±1.92	28.00±2.50	12.30±1.65	28.30±1.40	17.20±3.00	10	50
Total	135.26±0.57	225.12±0.65	133.54±1.20	150.93±0.70	131.30±1.42	142.64±1.54	100.00	200.00

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11359429>

Alkalinity (mg/L)								
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Table 2 showed the data for the pseudo-first order reactions in the surface water samples.

Table 2: Data for the pseudo-first order reactions in the Surface water samples.

Time/ Hr	Trend in TPH Reduction in the Bioremediation Method (mg/l) [X] _t	Ln[X] ₀ - [X] _t	Trend in TPH Reduction in the Silica Encapsulation Method (mg/l) [X] _t	Ln[X] ₀ - [X] _t	Trend in TPH Reduction in the Surfactant Method (mg/l) [X] _t	Ln[X] ₀ - [X] _t
0	4,960.40±2.80	0.00	5,11500±3.40	0.00	6,250.00±2.60	0.00
1	805.00±2.43	1.82	2,010.00±2.20	0.93	4,840.20±2.42	0.26
2	690.00±2.00	1.97	1,500.00±2.64	1.23	3,630.20±2.90	0.54
3	565.00±1.98	2.17	1,085.20±3.17	1.51	3,150.10±4.25	0.69
4	480.00±3.12	2.34	788. 20±3.67	1.87	2,145.20±3.75	0.86
5	400.00±2.72	2.52	650.30±5.65	2.06	1,109.40±2.86	1.07
6	369.25±3.10	2.60	479.20±3.18	2.38	1,550.10±2,79	1.39

Fig 1-3 showed the linear Pseudo – first order plot for TPH Reduction of water samples employing the bioremediation silica encapsulation and surfactant remediation respectively.

Fig 1: Pseudo – first order plot for TPH Reduction of water samples employing the bioremediation remediation method.

Fig 2: Pseudo – first order plot for TPH Reduction of water samples employing the Silica encapsulation remediation method.

Fig 3: Pseudo – first order plot for TPH Reduction of water samples employing the Surfactant remediation method.

Figure 4 showed a chart indicating the remediation efficiency of the various methods during experiment

Fig 4: Chart indicating the remediation efficiency of the various methods during Experiment

Discussions

Physicochemical Parameters

The results of the physicochemical parameters of the water samples are presented in Table 1

pH

pH refers to the measure of the acidity and basicity of a water medium. It is the logarithm of the reciprocal of the concentration of hydrogen ion ($pH = \text{Log } 1/H^+$).

Table 1 shows the resultant pH parameters for the surface water samples. From the results of the three remediation methods (bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant methods), the surface water samples accrued a pH range of 6.50 ± 1.05 - 6.90 ± 1.06 prior to analysis and after remediating on employing the various remediation techniques the pH had a slight increase and ranged between 8.20 ± 1.10 - 10.30 ± 1.08 . These were within the FMEnv standards permissible limit of 8.5-9.5 set by (FMEnv, 1991) and as such, posed no threat to the environ except for the Fenton oxidation and surfactant method that had a higher pH 10.30 as shown in table 1. This was found to be higher than the permissible limit of 6.5-9.5 set by (FMEnv, 1991) for drinking water /Agricultural uses. This is due to the alkalinity of the surfactant and other chemical reagents used for the remediation and would require a post treatment or a combination of biological treatment. Buragohain, (2013), combined Fenton/microbial treatment for the remediation of crude oil contaminated medium after one month of incubation and achieved a 75% degradation of the aliphatic fraction of the crude at pH range of 3 - 5.

Turbidity

Turbidity is the result of several factors including suspended soil particles, planktonic organisms and humic substances produced through decomposition of organic matter (FAO, 2002). It hinders the penetration of sunlight into the water body making it difficult for aquatic habitat to receive the positive effect of light (Ali *et al.*, 2012). Turbidity of water is an optical property that causes light to be scattered and absorbed, rather than transmitted.

Table 1 reveals the turbidity of the water samples. From the analysis, the turbidity of the polluted water samples, prior to analysis were recorded to be $1,250.10 \pm 16.50$ NTU, 584.33 ± 0.06 NTU and 559.20 ± 0.15 NTU for the bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant method respectively (Table 1). These values were relatively high and are an indicator that the water samples were polluted compared to 100-275 NTU turbidity values for highly polluted water reported by Rump, (1999). The exceptional high values for the bioremediation methods could be as a result of planktonic organisms and humic substances produced through decomposition of organic matter (FAO, 2002).

The chemical remediated samples for the various polluted water samples had turbidity ranges of 7.67 ± 0.12 - 10.30 ± 0.10 NTU. This indicated that the treated samples although not free from pollution in terms of turbidity, their levels had significantly dropped compared to the polluted samples.

Samples obtained from the bioremediation experiments had their turbidity values >1000 NTU. The exceptionally high values of turbidity from the bioremediation processes compared with those from chemical methods must be connected with the heavy organic load from the organic supplement used in the experiment and indicated high load of colloidal matter and by implication high concentrations of solids. The turbidity values from bioremediation work were found extremely higher than the 5.0 NTU permissible limit for turbidity recommended by (FMEnv, 1991) and (WHO, 1993).

Dissolved Oxygen (D.O)

Oxygen is one of the most important requirements for microbial degradation of hydrocarbons. Microorganisms deploy oxygen-incorporating enzymes to initiate attack on hydrocarbons. Oxygen is generally necessary for the initial breakdown of hydrocarbons, and subsequent reactions may also require direct incorporation of oxygen.

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11359429>

Dissolved oxygen is consumed by the degradation of organic matter in water and it is known that many fish kill are caused not from the direct toxicity of pollutant but from a deficiency of oxygen because of its consumption in the biodegradation of pollutants.

Table 1 shows the results of the dissolved oxygen prior to treatments. From the experiment, the mean values of the dissolved oxygen (D.O) of the polluted water samples were 3.20 ± 0.01 mg/l, 4.00 ± 0.10 mg/l and 4.30 ± 0.06 mg/l for the bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant method respectively. The low value of dissolved oxygen of the bioremediation water samples is an indication that most of the dissolved oxygen in the water samples had oxidized the organic content in the spilled oil to carbon (IV) oxide and water. The higher values of D.O in the chemical remediation methods could be as a result of less microbial activities as these samples were devoid of organic wastes amendment.

There was an increase in D.O mean values of the remediated water samples for the various remediation techniques employed though, not up to the FMEnv recommended standard values of 15.00 mg/l and WHO standard of 10.00 mg/l. From table 1, it can be seen that the bioremediated water sample had 4.50 ± 0.10 mg/l as compared with 3.20 ± 0.01 mg/l for the polluted sample recorded in table 1. The silica encapsulation and surfactant methods followed the same trend with mean values of 5.80 ± 0.12 mg/l and 4.80 ± 0.25 mg/l for the remediated samples (Table 1). The increase in the DO values for all treated samples after remediation in comparison with the DO values of the contaminated water samples showed that the quality of the polluted water samples had been improved after remediation had taken place. The evidence of remediation was clearly seen in the samples treated as there was significant improvement in their DO characterization (table 1). Evaluating the three remediation methods, the silica encapsulation method showed the highest increase in DO level (45%) followed by bioremediation method with an increase in DO level of 41%. The surfactant method had the lowest DO percentage increase of 11.63%. The bioremediation method, which had DO percentage increase of 41%, indicates some degree of efficiency in remediation but at a slower rate.

National Guidelines and Standards for Water Quality in Nigeria for drinking water (NSDWQ 2007) had recommended 7.50 mg/l of dissolved oxygen and the best of the dissolved oxygen results for the treated water samples had their values slightly lower than the above recommended value at the end of the remediation but however, greater than the 6 mg/l, dissolved oxygen requirement for good quality water in some sited literature (Rump, 1999). According to EPA classification (dissolved oxygen < 2 mg/l) could be fatal to most aquatic species while 5.0 - 6.0 mg/l are sufficient for the aquatic species, the latter condition was satisfied by all the remediated water samples. Threshold for dissolved oxygen is 5.0 mg/l for drinking water and could be more than 5.0 mg/l for agricultural purposes as reported by some authors.

Temperature

Temperature is an important parameter of water quality as it an indicator of the amount of dissolved oxygen available to aquatic organisms within the body of the water. It also has a direct influence on the biochemical reactions within the water sediment. More also, increases in water temperature are linked to increase in metabolic rates, which affect the biochemical oxygen decay and as well increases nitrification, photosynthesis and respiration.

Temperature of a water body may be influenced by a number of variables including geographic locations and depth (Ogbonna *et al.*, 2021). The mean temperature of the surface water samples were $28.70^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.20$, $28.65^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.25$ and $28.50^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.05$ for the bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant method respectively. These values are below the range of WHO standards for normal drinking water and may be due to the effect of crude oil contamination of the surface water samples. Contamination of water body by crude oil may lead to odour and eutrophication of the entire water system.

Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD₅)

BOD₅ is the amount of oxygen required by the aerobic bacteria to biochemically oxidize the organic matter present in the polluted samples

The results of the biological oxygen demand of the surface water samples are shown in table 1.

The polluted water samples accrued BOD₅ mean values of 11.30 ± 1.20 mg/l, 9.20 ± 2.00 mg/l and 9.50 ± 0.80 mg/l on commencement of analysis for the bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant method respectively. The increased values of BOD in all the samples after on commencement of analysis suggest that the oxygen in the polluted water samples is being used by the aerobic bacteria to oxidize the organic matter present in the surface water samples and could be attributed to high percentage of organic matter present in the sample (Table 1). Manhokwe, (2015), had reported the oxygen demand of water and wastewater to be proportional to the amount of organic matter present. The normal range of BOD for good water quality is 5-7.5 mg/l.

After remediation, percentage reductions in BOD mean values of 90.00, 88.10 and 35.65 was observed for the bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant methods respectively. The low reduction value of 35.65% observed for the surfactant method could be attributed to the nature of surfactant used for the remediation.

Among the three remediated water samples, the polluted water samples had BOD₅ range between 4.70 ± 1.53 mg/l - 8.45 ± 0.16 mg/l after remediation.

Generally, the sample with the bioremediation method had the highest BOD₅ percentage reduction of 90.00 followed by the sample treated silica encapsulation method which was observed to have a BOD₅ percentage reduction of 88.10 while the water samples treated with the surfactant method had the lowest reduction of 35.25%. The subsequent drops in BOD₅ values in all treated samples corroborated the fact that remediation had taken at place at varying degrees. The bioremediation and silica encapsulation treated water samples had their BOD₅ values within the safe limit of (7.5mg/l) recommended for quality drinking water in Nigeria (FMEnv, 1991) while the surfactant treated samples had their BOD₅ mean values above the FMEnv standards as seen in table 1.

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

COD is the amount of chemical oxidant required for the oxidation of organic matter present in polluted water samples.

Table 1 shows the results of the chemical oxygen demand (COD) of the surface water samples. Prior to analysis, the water sample for the bioremediation method, silica encapsulation and surfactant methods were 388 ± 0.20 , 315.75 ± 0.50 and 322.42 ± 0.30 mg/l respectively (Table 1). The COD being a measure of the total oxidizable organic matter is expected to increase in a polluted water medium. The remediated samples accrued mean values of 35.25 ± 0.20 , 67.55 ± 0.15 and 80.60 ± 0.16 mg/l respectively.

The observed COD drop for the water samples in the bioremediation method was possibly due to some aromatic hydrocarbons, straight-chain aliphatic and nitrogenous compounds present crude oil that was not readily oxidized and this agreed with the findings of Medjor, (2013). From the remediation methods employed, a reduction value was observed to be 90.91%, 78.61% and 75.00% respectively. The COD/BOD ratio of all the treated water was relatively very low compared with those obtained prior to treatment.

Low COD/BOD ratio shows low concentration of oxidizable organic matter and high ratio indicates high levels of oxidizable organic matter in water/wastewater (Suzane and Nielson, 2002). The significant reduction of COD in all treated water samples indicate that effective remediation had taken place. The treated water samples had their COD values within the 40 mg/l safe permissible limit for quality drinking water in Nigeria (FMEnv, 1991).

Electrical Conductivity

Conductivity is an indirect measure of the salinity of the water. Fish and other organisms that live in freshwater cannot tolerate large increases in the saltiness of the water because they will not be able to keep water in their bodies. Fish and animals that live in saltier water such as in the ocean are adapted to these environments and can survive.

Climate change may increase the salinity of freshwater lakes if warmer conditions increase evaporation (Wetzel, 1983). This could result in stress to fish and other animals that live in water. Pollution can also increase conductivity of lakes and rivers because industrial and human wastewaters often have high conductivity. However, not all industrial activities will increase water conductivity. For example, oil does not conduct electricity well, so water pollution by oil would not be detected by measuring water conductivity. Low conductivity ($0-200\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) is an indicator of pristine or background conditions. Mid - range conductivity ($200-1000\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) is the normal background for most major rivers. Conductivity outside this range could indicate that the water is not suitable for certain species of fish or bugs. High conductivity (1000 to $10,000\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) is an indicator of saline conditions. Waters that have been heavily impacted by industry can fall into this range.(U.S. E.P.A. Conductivity (<http://water.epa.gov/type/rs/monitoring/vms59.cfm>).

Table 1 shows the results of the electrical conductivity found in the surface water samples. The trends observed in electrical conductivity values is the reverse case for values obtained for salinity of a water medium.

The electrical conductivity value for the control water sample in the bioremediation method was $1,210.00\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ while that for the water sample, prior to treatment was $106.00 \pm 2.5\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, as presented in table 1. The low value of electrical conductivity of the contaminated water sample prior to treatment may probably be attributed to the presence of organic carbon chains in the water samples. This would have led to a non-polar medium resulting in the retardation of ionic movement in the water solution and in

turn leading to electrical conductivity reduction. Medjor, (2013), in his finding, had noted that the crude oil, being predominantly consisted of non-polar organic fractions had no tendency to conduct electrical current. The electrical conductivity value of the treated water sample from the biological method had a mean value of ranged from $1,118 \pm 1.5\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, the silica encapsulation method accrued a mean value of $1,108.30 \pm 1.00 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ while the surfactant method was $950.00 \pm 1.30\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. These electrical conductivity values were notably high and could probably be due to the addition of ions/salts obtained from the organic wastes and chemical reagents used for the remediation experiment. More also, some amount of organic matter had been removed from the contaminated water samples thereby promoting ion mobility. From the results, electrical conductivity values increased in all the samples and that is a good indication that remediation at varying degree had occurred in all the remediated samples. The results from the chemical remediated sample were all within the $1,200\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ water standard threshold set by FMEnv, 1991) agricultural purposes while that of the bioremediated samples were above the required standard set by FMEnv, 1991).

Total Alkalinity

Alkalinity is the sum of components (mainly bicarbonate, carbonate, and hydroxide) in the water that tend to elevate the pH of the water above 4.5. These factors are characteristic of the source of water and the natural processes taking place at any given time. Alkalinity represents the buffering capacity of water and its ability to resist a change in pH. Alken-Murray recommends alkalinity above 75 mg/l to offset acid produced by bacteria nitrifying ammonia and the acceptable range for most aquatic organisms is between 20-200 mg/l (ppm) (www.alkenmurray.com/TESTS01.htm). It is defined is the acid neutralizing capacity of water and a function of all titratable bases present in water (Denloye, (2004).

Table 1 shows the total alkalinity of the water samples. The control water sample had an alkalinity concentration of 156.00mg/l while the water sample prior to analysis, had a mean value of 135.26 ± 0.57 mg/l in the bioremediation experiment. The decrease observed in the alkalinity values recorded was likely due to chemical interaction between the acidic components of the contaminants and the carbonates or hydroxyl ions present in the water sample. The remediated water samples obtained from the bioremediation method had alkalinity value of 225.12 ± 0.65 mg/l (Table 1). For the bioremediation process alkalinity is the best medium for biological activity that is for measuring the waste product of microbial activity. The increase in the alkalinity values for the water samples obtained from the bioremediation indicated that biodegradation has taken place.

Range of alkalinity concentrations between 142.64 ± 1.54 - 150.93 ± 0.70 mg/l was recorded for the water samples treated with the chemical method. All the treated samples had their alkalinity levels above the 100mg/l desirable level recommended for quality drinking water in Nigeria (FMEnv, 1991). In all, the water samples were within the recommended level safe for aquatic life except the bio remediated water samples that were slightly higher than the 200mg/l recommended for aquatic life.

Nitrate (NO_3)

Water quality monitoring shows that nitrate-nitrogen ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) is present in surface water at relatively low concentrations of between (0–18mg/l) but can reach high levels as a result of agricultural runoff, oil spill, refuse dump runoff or contamination with human or animal wastes (USEPA, 1987). The

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11359429>

concentration often fluctuates with the season and may increase when the river is fed by nitrate-rich aquifers. Nitrate concentrations have gradually increased in many European countries in the last few decades and have sometimes doubled over the past 20 years. In the USA, nitrates are present in most surface water and groundwater supplies at levels below 4 mg/l, with levels exceeding 20 mg/l in about 3% of surface waters and 6% of ground waters (USEPA, 1987). In addition, a nitrate concentration of 44 mg/l (10 mg of nitrate-nitrogen per litre) was exceeded in 40 surface water and 568 groundwater supplies in 1986 as noted by these authors. In the United Kingdom, for example, an average annual increase of 0.7 mg/l has been observed in some rivers (Young & Morgan-Jones, 1980)

The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has adopted the 10mg/l standard as the Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) for Nitrate-Nitrogen and 50mg/l recommended level for quality drinking water in Nigeria (FMEnv, 1991). Nitrate concentration above the FMEnv recommended value of 10mg/l is dangerous to pregnant women and poses a serious health threat to infants less than 3 - 6 months of age. Nitrate, by itself is not harmful but when converted to highly toxic dioxonitrate (III), NO_2 by certain bacteria commonly found in the intestinal tract of infants has devastating effects on infant health. Nitrate III causes a disease condition known as methemoglobinemia (blue baby syndrome) [Fecham *et al.*, 1986; Groen *et al.*, 1988]. Nitrates have the potential to cause diuresis, increased starchy deposits and haemorrhaging the spleen following a lifetime exposure. Nitrates have a high potential to migrate to water since they are very soluble in water and do not bind to soil (Punmia *et al.*, 1998).

Table 1 shows the nitrate concentration of the water samples. The control water samples for the bioremediation method had nitrate concentration of 24mg/l while that of the sample prior to treatment was recorded as 36.00 ± 2.0 mg/l, as shown in Table 1. After remediation, the water samples had a nitrate concentration of 21.00 ± 1.92 mg/l. This is far above the 10mg/l standard recommended by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 1991 as the Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) but still within the standard threshold of 50mg/l allowed for drinking water by FMEnv, 1991) and could be due to the presence of urea or uric acid contained in the organic manure that was used as biostimulation during the bioremediation analysis.

The chemical remediated water samples had nitrate concentration of 6.0mg/l in the control sample (Table 1). The remediated water samples had nitrate concentrations ranging from 12.30 ± 1.65 - 17.20 ± 3.00 mg/l as seen in Table 1. The chemical remediated water samples had their nitrate levels slightly higher than the 10mg/l standard for Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) adopted for Nitrate-Nitrogen (EPA) and could be due to high percentage crude contamination.

Ammonia (NH_3)

Table 1 shows the ammonia concentration of the water samples. In the three types of remediation method employed in this study, the control water sample mean value was 0.67mg/l. The water samples prior to treatment accrued nitrogen concentration mean value of 0.22 ± 0.75 mg/l during the bioremediation analysis. High ammonia concentrations of 3.10 ± 0.58 mg/l was observed after remediation as recorded in table 1 and this could be because of the organic supplement used in the biological method which resulted in the conversion of nitrates into NH_3 by the denitrifying bacteria called denitrificants. Water sample with ammonia level between 0.3-100mg/l is contaminated and contains only putrefying bacteria with no higher organisms (Rump, 1999)

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11359429>

The chemical remediated samples accrued ammonia concentrations ranging between $(0.42 \pm 0.17 - 0.48 \pm 0.70 \text{ mg/l})$. Comparing the control values of 0.67 mg/l with that of the samples prior to analysis which ranged between $0.20 \pm 1.50 - 0.33 \pm 0.63 \text{ mg/}$, the low value of ammonia in the water sample was probably due to chemical interaction between the ammonia in the water sample and the acidic components in crude oil that contaminated the water medium. Jons *et al.*, (2001) had noted that up to 3% w/w of crude oil may be acids of which naphthenic acids are most abundant.

In general, ammonia concentrations for the biological treated samples were found to be higher than the recommended level for ammonia (0.5 mg/l) in quality drinking water in Nigeria (FMEnv, 1991) and therefore not too safe for agriculture purposes and aquatic lives.

Phosphate PO_3^{4-}

Table 1 shows the results of the phosphate concentration in the surface water samples. From the bioremediation analysis, the phosphate concentration in the control water sample was 0.22 mg/l while that of the water sample prior to treatment was $0.36 \pm 0.06 \text{ mg/l}$. The increase in the phosphate levels in the water sample compared with that of the control water sample may be due to contributions of phosphate as chemical components from the contaminant. After remediation, phosphate value was recorded to be $0.04 \pm \text{mg/l}$ (Table 1).

In the chemical-treated water samples, concentration of phosphate was between $0.06 \pm 0.03 - 0.07 \pm 0.08 \text{ mg/l}$ after remediation. Phosphate concentrations were high and above the 0.02 mg/l maximum acceptable limit. Esry *et al.*, (1991) had reported that traces of phosphate may increase the tendency of troublesome algae bloom in water. This could lead to excessive fertilization and eutrophication resulting to choked waterways being choked up and excess demand of dissolved oxygen. When these water plants die, there will be excessive decay and putrefaction which may also kill fishes.

Remediation Kinetics

Reaction rates are usually determined by measuring the decrease in concentration of a reactant or the increase in concentration of a product with time. It is of paramount importance in kinetic studies to predict if chemical species will affect the rate at which a chemical reaction proceeds (Helmenstine, 2017).

Kinetics of the three remediation methods were investigated for their order of reactions.

The concentration of residual TPH after reaction was plotted for each of the methods as seen in figures 1. In all cases, TPH diminished with time and this is a strong indication that the reacting species of the treatment solution had a strong interaction with the TPH molecules of the sample medium. Pseudo rate order plots for the remediation process were tested using the pseudo first order equations of $\text{Ln}[X]_0 - \text{Ln}[X]_t$ against time and second order; $t/q_t = 1/K_2q_e^2 + 1/q_e t$. The results of the plots were linear as regression coefficient in each case, were found to be close to 1 (≥ 0.9). Pseudo first order equation was employed and thus the latter was discarded. The pseudo first order rate constants K, for the bioremediation, Silica encapsulation and Surfactant method were $9.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mg}^{-1} \text{ Lhr}^{-1}$, $1.7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mg}^{-1} \text{ Lhr}^{-1}$ and $2.3 \times 10^2 \text{ mg}^{-1} \text{ Lhr}^{-1}$ respectively. Large K values signifies a fast reaction while small values of K signifies a relatively slow reaction and as such, the K values calculated from the slope of the graphs quite

agrees with the experimental data indicating that the bioremediation method had the slowest rate of reaction while silica encapsulation method had the fastest rate.

Fig 1 indicates the linear plot of the graphs and the regression coefficient. R^2 for the pseudo first order fittings were high (close to 1) in all the samples and therefore it can be inferred that the first order equation fits well with the experimental data.

Figure 4 reveals the optimum remediation efficiency of the three methods employed at the end of experiment. In the bioremediation method, on administering the second dose of treatment, the highest percentage remediation of 94.48 was achieved while optimum remediation was obtained on administering the first dose for the silica encapsulation and surfactant methods (94.11 and 92.56. The reason for this could be that contaminant concentration would have been too low on a first dose and could not generate enough microbes for effective remediation for the bioremediation method hence optimum remediation was achieved on application of the second dose.

Conclusion

With the expected increase in exploration of crude oil and production operations of its derivatives, there are major concerns over the possibility of a subsurface blowout of large oil spills in marine environment and the inadequacy of quick response to its management. This had led the researcher to access three remediation techniques in treatment of surface water samples as a way to proffer solution to these challenges. Assessing the three methods employed for the remediation of the surface water samples, the bioremediation method, though took a longer time of 1008 hrs to achieve optimum remediation had the highest percentage remediation of 94.48. Considering the chemical remediation methods, silica encapsulation had the best percentage remediation of 94.11 though at a slower rate of 144 hrs at the end of experiment while the surfactant method gave percentage remediation of 92.56. The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the effectiveness and efficiency of remediation of the three methods (bioremediation, silica encapsulation and surfactant methods) used in the treatments of the samples, showed that there was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) at 95% confidence level but in terms of the levels of contamination, there was a significant difference in the treatment dosage ($P < 0.05$) at 95 confidence level.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this research work, the following suggestions were made:

In the event of a large oil spill, invariably all compartments of the marine habitat such as the water surface, water column, sediments, and shoreline would likely be impacted and as such, only one single spill response strategy is unlikely to provide optimal protection. Therefore, effort should be made by management bodies to adopt two or multiple techniques.

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Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11359429>

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